

D6.1

Dissemination and Communication Plan

WHITE

October 2022

PROJECT INFORMATION

PROGRAMME	Horizon Europe
TOPIC	HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07
TYPE OF ACTION	HORIZON-CSA
PROJECT NUMBER	101059785
START DAY	1 June 2022
DURATION	36 months

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

TITLE	Dissemination and Communication Plan
WORK PACKAGE	6
TASK	T6.1 Dissemination and communication activities
AUTHORS (Organisation)	Antonia-Areti Kalimeri (WHITE), Pinelopi Kaslama (WHITE)
REVIEWERS	All partners
DATE	31 October 2022

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public, fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
Classified R-UE/EU-R	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified C-UE/EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified S-UE/EU-S	EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444	

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Changes	Responsible partner
0.1	29/09/2022	First draft ready for internal review	WHITE
0.2	7/10/2022	Reviewers' feedback	All partners
0.3	20/10/2022	Final draft (incorporated feedback)	WHITE
1.0	21/10/2022	Final deliverable sent to the coordinator	WHITE
1.0	31/10/2022	Submission	WR
2.0		EU disclaimer update (short version)	

LEGAL NOTICE

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

© SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Consortium, 2022

Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
1. INTRODUCTION.....	10
2. ABOUT SUSTCERT4BIOBASED PROJECT.....	11
3. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGY	12
3.1 Overview	12
3.2 Objectives of the DCP	13
4. TARGET AUDIENCE AND KEY MESSAGES	14
4.1 Target audience	14
4.2 Key messages and vision	18
4.2.1 Key messages.....	18
5. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION TOOLS AND CHANNELS	21
5.1 Promotional material	23
5.1.1 Project logo	23
5.1.2 Leaflet and poster.....	24
5.1.3 Publication templates	24
5.1.4 Promotional video.....	24
5.1.5 Other promotional material	24
5.2 Digital tools	25
5.2.1 SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website.....	25
5.2.2 Newsletter	25
5.2.3 Social Media Accounts (SMA)	26
5.3 Events	30
5.3.1 Project's events	30
5.3.2 External events and conferences	32
5.4 Publications.....	33
5.4.1 Scientific publications	33
5.4.2 Non-scientific publications	34
6. ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES.....	35
7. NETWORKS AND SYNERGIES.....	36
8. MONITORING, EVALUATION AND REPORTING FRAMEWORK.....	40

8.1	Monitoring and evaluation	40
8.2	Reporting	41
9.	TIMELINE AND IMPLEMENTATION PLAN	42
10.	CONCLUSIONS	45
11.	ANNEX.....	46
11.1	Annex I – Dissemination and communication guidelines	46
11.2	Annex II – Dissemination and communication monitoring template	50
11.3	Annex III – Events’ reporting template	51
11.4	Annex IV – External conferences and events identification template	55

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Overview of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED’s D&C strategy	12
Figure 2. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED target audiences	14
Figure 3. Stakeholder mapping and types of stakeholder engagement.....	15
Figure 4. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED’s communication activities.....	21
Figure 5. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project logo.....	23
Figure 6. The EU funding properly acknowledged.	24
Figure 7. Screenshot of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED’S Facebook page	29
Figure 8. Screenshot of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED’S Twitter account	30
Figure 9. Screenshot of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED’S LinkedIn account.....	30
Figure 10. Summary of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED’S timeline	42

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Summary of D&C's key questions	10
Table 2. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED target audience categories	16
Table 3. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED target audience, needs and messages	19
Table 4. Tools and channels used for the identified target groups	22
Table 5. The target audiences addressed by each social media channel	27
Table 6. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED’S internal events	31
Table 7. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED’S external events and conferences	32
Table 8. Indicative list of pre-selected scientific journals for SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's papers.....	34
Table 9. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED’S dissemination networks	36
Table 10. Projects for potential synergies	37
Table 11. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED’S Key Performance Indicators	40
Table 12. List with Annexes for Dissemination.....	41
Table 13. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED’s Timeline and objectives	43

ABBREVIATIONS

CA	Consortium Agreement
CIRCE	Centro de Investigación de Recursos y Consumos Energéticos
CU	Control Union Certifications Germany GmbH
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
EC	European Commission
ECOS	Environmental Coalition on Standards
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NoI	Network of Interest
PAB	Project Advisory Board
PC	Project Coordinator
SMA s	Social Media Accounts
WEcR	Wageningen Economic Research
WFBR	Wageningen Food and Biobased Research
WHITE	White Research SRL
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
WR	Wageningen Research

Executive Summary

This report constitutes the first version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) of the Horizon Europe SUSTCERT4BIOBASED (Sustainability Certification for Biobased Systems) project. The DCP will present the overall strategy that will guide the consortium's communication and dissemination activities during the project's implementation. Its purpose is to set a plan for the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project communication strategy and to maximize the impact throughout its lifecycle.

The report outlines the dissemination and communication strategy of the project, describes the management of the dissemination activities and sets up a detailed monitoring process to ensure its successful implementation. The plan aims to engage a wide range of relevant groups and maximise the project's impact by spreading its outcomes and messages to all the targeted stakeholders and to the general public.

The main sections of this document are presented below:

Chapter 1: An *introduction* to the DCP and its goals.

Chapter 2: A brief description of the *SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project*.

Chapter 3: The *overview of the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Strategy* and its objectives

Chapter 4: The *targeted audience* and the respective key messages for the identified stakeholders

Chapter 5: The *tools and channels* used to disseminate and communicate the project's activities and results to the identified targeted stakeholders

Chapter 6: This section describes the *roles and responsibilities* of the dissemination manager and the consortium partners for the successful deployment of the D&C strategy.

Chapter 7: The importance of *establishing synergies* with other relevant projects and networks throughout the duration of the project is elaborated in this chapter.

Chapter 8: This section outlines the *Key Performance Indicators* that will be used for the *evaluation* of the dissemination efforts and will permit us to adopt the best practices to increase project's impact. In addition, the *reporting process* regarding the dissemination activities is also described.

Chapter 9: The *timeline* of the four different stages for the implementation of the project's dissemination activities is briefly described in this section.

In the Annex are listed:

- **The dissemination and communication guidelines:** This is a document that was circulated to the consortium and highlights important aspects of the dissemination and communication activities.
- **The dissemination and communication reporting template:** This is the template that all partners need to update in a monthly basis with information about all the dissemination and communication activities.
- **Events' reporting template:** The document that all partners need to fill in after the organisation or their participation in an event.

- **External conferences and events identification template:** This is a template that partners should send to WHITE when an interesting relevant event or conference is identified.

1. Introduction

It is fundamental to disseminate and effectively communicate the project's vision and results to ensure the successful implementation of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED. In this context, this document includes the Dissemination and Communication Plan of the project and describes the operational framework for its deployment.

The main objective of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Strategy is to define the actions carried out and the tools to be used for the promotion of the project's results. On top of that, the strategy aims to provide a specific plan to raise awareness around the project and support the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's implementation in line with the contractual obligations. Thus, besides supporting the exploitation of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED outcomes the DCP will ensure the sustainability of the assets developed during the project's lifecycle.

In particular, the DCP offers the answers to some fundamental questions about the communication and dissemination activities of the project:

Table 1. Summary of D&C's key questions

Key questions	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's DCP
What?	Key messages
To Whom?	Target audiences
Who?	Roles & Responsibilities
How?	Communication tools and channels, guidelines, and templates
When?	Timeline

The dissemination and communication activities will be carried out throughout the duration of the project under the dedicated work package (WP6 - Dissemination and communication activities). Through these activities the project aspires to engage a large number of stakeholders who could further spread the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's vision and results to wider audiences through their networks, influence and impact. In addition, the interaction with relevant stakeholders will enable us to receive constant feedback on the project's outcomes.

The DCP, the guidelines and templates, as well as the Annexes produced in this report will be subjects to updates in line with the project's progress. The experience and lessons learnt throughout the implementation of the project will permit us to update and modify the strategy - when needed - to be tailored to the needs of our vision. The final version of the D&C strategy is already foreseen by M36 and will ensure the continuation of the dissemination of the results even after the completion of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED.

The DCP will be updated - when necessary - to be in line with the project's requirements and progress.

2. About SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project

Biobased products play a prominent role in the transition from a fossil-based economy to a circular economy at an EU and global level. According to an assessment done by the European Commission, biobased products can contribute to a more sustainable economy and could represent approximately €57 billion in annual income and involve 300.000 jobs¹.

But what are exactly the biobased products? **Biobased products are wholly or partly derived from materials of biological origin.** Even though they could help reduce greenhouse gas emissions and offer other advantages such as lower levels of toxicity or novel product characteristics (e.g., biodegradability), it is still very important to **ensure their sustainability on environmental, social and economic dimensions.**

There are plenty of sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels that have been developed to track the sustainability impacts of biobased products. However, given the fact that there is no harmonization of these certification schemes yet, **the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project will contribute to defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainable certification schemes and business-to-business labels.** The project will lay the foundation to support **a faster and smoother transition to a circular and sustainable bioeconomy.**

It will do so by developing a monitoring system to evaluate the effectiveness and robustness of existing certifications schemes and labels and assessing the feasibility of adoption of certification schemes and labels by taking into consideration costs and benefits (including internalized environmental and social ones). The results of the project as well as the insights gained along the way will be used to provide recommendations to four key target groups: policy makers, sustainability system community, industrial biobased value chain actors, and regional bioeconomy stakeholders.

Thus, the overall objectives of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED are:

- To **review and analyse** the existing international and EU sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for biological resources and for biobased materials and products.
- To **create a database** of the global trade flows for biological resources and for biobased materials and products distinguishing between certified and uncertified.
- To **develop a monitoring framework** for the systematic evaluation of the effectiveness and robustness of the existing sustainability schemes and labels.
- To use the developed monitoring framework to assess the existing schemes and **identify the “best-in-class”** among them.
- To **assess the costs and benefits** from the adoption of certification schemes and labels in selected industrial biobased value chains.
- To identify best practices and **offer recommendations** for the adoption of effective and robust sustainability schemes and labels.
- To **engage a variety of relevant stakeholders** especially international organisations, industrial parties, scheme owners, certifications bodies and policy makers.

¹ https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/biotechnology/bio-based-products_en

Within the next years the multidisciplinary consortium of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project will organize several events and workshops to inform the audience about important findings and updates on the progress of the project.

Lastly, the dimension of sustainability is pivotal to the goals of the project. As such, the dissemination and communication efforts are vital for the maximization of its impact and value extraction. Creating multiple channels for taking advantage of the project assets is a key priority for SUSTCERT4BIOBASED and it becomes apparent that dissemination and communication activities are significant, as they leverage the sustainability of the project's positive impacts.

3. Dissemination and communication strategy

3.1 Overview

The DCP of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED describes the overall D&C strategy of the project concerning the dissemination and communication of the outcomes. The strategy is carefully designed and tailored to the approach of the project aiming to maximise its impact, transfer knowledge and the results to the targeted stakeholders, as well as to communicate its concept to wider audiences. The D&C strategy is translated into an actionable plan by considering multiple key elements as illustrated in the figure below and described in the next chapters.

Figure 1. Overview of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's D&C strategy

This section presents the overview of the D&C strategy and outlines the structure of the DCP. First of all, the first sub-section presents the objectives of the DCP which will be used to monitor the successful implementation of the strategy. The fourth chapter defines the target audience to whom we will disseminate the project's results. On top of that, the next sub-section presents the key

messages for each one of the targeted stakeholders, as well as the core visions and assets. A dedicated section of the strategy will focus on the means, channels, and tools that will be used to reach the identified stakeholders. Additionally, the allocation of roles and responsibilities for the dissemination strategy will be clearly elaborated to ensure the smooth and effective implementation of the DCP.

Throughout the duration of the project, special attention will be given to the cooperation with other relevant projects at national and European level. Although there is a dedicated task (T6.3) for establishing synergies with other relevant projects and networks, the document presents a short introduction regarding the initial plan. Lastly, the next chapters unveil a robust framework for the assessment of the strategy along with a timeline for the dissemination and communication steps.

Aiming to ensure the successful dissemination and communication of results, the DCP constitutes a guidelines document that presents the tools and actions which will navigate the consortium partners to successfully engage the targeted stakeholders. Of course, the DCP should not be seen as a static document but instead as a dynamic flexible strategy that will be reviewed and updated - if this is necessary - during the lifecycle of the project.

3.2 Objectives of the DCP

The D&C strategy of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED sets a list of practical and realistic objectives that will ensure the effective monitoring and consequently the successful implementation of the dissemination and communication activities of the project. These objectives answer to the question of WHY the DCP is needed. The dissemination and communication objectives of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED are briefly presented below:

- Present the project's aim, vision, activities and events to a wider audience
- Promote awareness raising among stakeholder groups
- Encourage involvement in the project's activities
- Engage stakeholders through a series of relevant activities, events and conferences
- Ensure that the key messages are communicated to its target audiences
- Ensure the exploitation of the project's outcomes
- Introduce scientific concepts in an easy to grasp way to stakeholders and citizens
- Plan, organise, run, monitor and fine-tune the project's dissemination activities and events
- Establish and sustain synergies with other relevant national and European projects and networks
- Disseminate the project's lessons learnt and outcomes in an open and transparent way
- Establish an active community exchanging ideas and knowledge in topics relevant to the project (e.g., sustainability certifications for biobased systems)

Overall, the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED objectives could be generally summarised as follows:

- ✓ Present
- ✓ Explain
- ✓ Raise awareness
- ✓ Mobilise
- ✓ Empower
- ✓ Communicate
- ✓ Open dialogues

4. Target audience and key messages

4.1 Target audience

One of the most critical steps for the successful development of the D&C strategy is to answer the question “to Whom?”. Who are the main stakeholders that the project aims to engage and transfer its messages and results? This section presents the main target audiences that SUSTCERT4BIOBASED expects to reach during its lifecycle. The figure below briefly presents the target audiences:

Figure 2. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED target audiences

Particularly, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED aims to engage a wide variety of stakeholders with different backgrounds and experiences. In particular:

The project’s **primary targets** are:

1. Scheme and label owners
2. Certification bodies
3. Standardization community
4. Governments (national and local) & policy makers
5. Regional bioeconomy & sustainability actors
6. Industrial actors

Besides the main stakeholders’ audiences, the project aims to share its message also to:

7. Academia & scientific community
8. Non-governmental organisations (NGOs)
9. Relevant projects and initiatives
10. General public
11. International organizations

During the project’s lifespan, it remains important to classify them to better prioritise and fine-tune our engagement efforts. To this aim, the Stakeholders Classification Model¹ will be used in order to classify each targeted stakeholder group based on the following parameters:

- The extent of a stakeholder’s power/authority;
- The stakeholder’s interest regarding the outcomes of the project;
- The extent of the stakeholder’s active involvement in the project;
- The level of stakeholder’s influence over the project planning and/or outcomes.

The classification of the targeted stakeholders’ groups will be used in order to tailor the communicated messages and adopt the optimum tools and dissemination channels for each one of the groups. The following figure depicts the parameters and how they define different types of stakeholder engagement:

Figure 3. Stakeholder mapping and types of stakeholder engagement

The D&C strategy aims to reach the above mentioned identified audiences which were further categorised into the broader SUSTCERT4BIOBASED stakeholder groups. A more detailed elaboration on the targeted stakeholders and specific examples are offered in the following Table:

¹ Emerson Wagner Mainardes, Helena Alves, Mário Raposo, (2012). “A model for stakeholder classification and stakeholder relationships”, Management Decision, Vol. 50 Issue: 10, pp. 1861-1879.

Table 2. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED target audience categories

Target Group	Short description	Sub-categories	Example of stakeholders
Sustainability system actors	All actors that are active in the field of certification, bioeconomy, sustainability.	<p>Scheme/Label owners</p> <p>Standardisation bodies</p> <p>Certification bodies</p>	<p>ISEAL is the global membership organisation for ambitious, collaborative and transparent sustainability systems.</p> <p>NEN: the Royal Netherlands Standardization Institute</p> <p>RSB: the Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials (offers certification schemes)</p> <p>ISCC: International Sustainability and Carbon Certification (offers certification schemes)</p> <p>REDCert: Offers certification schemes for sustainably produced biomass</p> <p>SGS: Testing, inspection and certification company</p> <p>GEN: Global Ecolabelling Network is a non-profit association of leading ecolabelling organisations worldwide</p>
Policy actors	Decision-makers at European, national, and regional level who are expected to play a key role in policy design.	<p>EU policy makers</p> <p>Policy advisors</p> <p>Governments</p>	<p>Policy officers at Directorates-General of the EC (for example DG-RTD, DG-ENV, DG-AGRI)</p> <p>Policy officers at EU Member States (for example Dutch Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality)</p>

Industrial actors	Industry associations operating in the field of bioeconomy at a European or global level.	Industrial biobased value chain actors Biomass producers Industrial operators and traders	BIC: Biobased Industries Consortium EUBP: European Bioplastics EUBA: The European Bioeconomy Alliance EUBIA: European Biomass Industry Association ERRMA: European Renewable Raw Materials Association CEFIC: European Chemical Industry Council
Regional bioeconomy stakeholders	Local governments, regions, municipalities and networks that are active in the field of bioeconomy.	Local authorities Networks for regional development Farmers Unions Entrepreneurs	EIP-AGRI: The European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural productivity and Sustainability BIOEAST: The Central-Eastern European Initiative for Knowledge-based Agriculture, Aquaculture and Forestry in the Bioeconomy SPRING: Italian Cluster of Circular Bioeconomy Bioeconomy Network Initiative of the Metropolitan Region Rhine-Neckar GmbH
Scientific community	Network of interacting scientists who conduct research in the fields of bioeconomy and biobased products, standardisation, sustainability etc.	Research Centres Research groups Individual researchers Universities	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy – Joint Research Centre (JRC) Hohenheim Research Centre for Bioeconomy Bioeconomy Science Centre CREA: Research Centre for Agricultural Policies and Bioeconomy EuBioNet: The European Bioeconomy Network (alliance of EU projects)
NGOs	Organisations active in the areas of environmental conservation and preventing degradation of natural resources	NGOs	WWF: World Wide Fund for Nature ZWE: Zero Waste Europe EEB: European Environmental Bureau FERN: Making the EU work for people and forests BirdLife International

International organizations	Organisations that are active globally in the bioeconomy area	International organisations Platforms for international cooperation	<p>OECD: Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development</p> <p>FAO: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations</p> <p>UNEP: United Nations Environment Program</p> <p>UNFSS: The United Nation Forum on Sustainability Standards</p> <p>IUCN: International Union for Conservation of Nature</p> <p>IRP: International Resource Panel</p> <p>IBF: International Bioeconomy Forum</p>
Relevant EU projects & initiatives	Both ongoing and completed European projects which focus on related disciplines to SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 projects Other European and national projects.	HARMONITOR, STAR4BBS, STAR-ProBio, BioMonitor, BIORECER, SUSTRACK, FOODCoST, WaysTUP!, Star4BBI, BIOSWITCH, AllThings.Bio etc.
Society	Individuals who are interested in enhancing their knowledge on biobased products and the certification process.	General public Civil society organizations	Civil Society Organizations Individuals

4.2 Key messages and vision

4.2.1 Key messages

Another important step for establishing a successful D&C strategy is to determine WHAT will be communicated to the stakeholders. In the previous section, a first identification of the most critical stakeholders' groups to be reached in the framework of the project took place. These groups consist of stakeholders with different backgrounds and needs and therefore different messages should be communicated to them. These messages will be updated over the course of the project based on the experience acquired during the implementation of the activities. Furthermore, the project aims to exploit the extended network of the consortium partners in order to reach a wide pool of individuals. In the table below are enlisted the targeted stakeholder groups along with their needs and tailored messages. However, the final key messages will be defined throughout the project's lifecycle based on the actual SUSTCERT4BIOBASED data and outcomes.

Table 3. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED target audience, needs and messages

Target Group	Needs	Messages
Sustainability system actors	<p>To enhance the adoption of their certification schemes/labels in the market.</p> <p>To increase credibility of their certification schemes.</p> <p>To keep certification standards up to date based on scientific research findings.</p> <p>To engage with the certification community.</p> <p>To exchange best practices on the improvement of the certification process.</p> <p>To explore synergies and collaboration.</p>	<p>How to increase the adoption of effective schemes.</p> <p>How to enhance the performance of certification schemes.</p> <p>Provide a network with other actors who are active in the field of certification for further collaboration.</p>
Policy actors	<p>To understand the current landscape of biobased value chains and the extent of their certification.</p> <p>To monitor the progress in the field of biobased economy certification systems and support their harmonization.</p> <p>To have actual data and consistent information on the current developments in the certification field.</p>	<p>How to incorporate certification schemes into policy measures.</p> <p>Provide data and figures on trade of the biological resources and biobased materials and their level of certification.</p> <p>How the monitoring system can be integrated into the policy process.</p>
Industrial actors	<p>To get clear information on the existing certification schemes/labels.</p> <p>To understand the costs and benefits from the adoption of certification schemes/labels.</p> <p>To stay competitive and be considered credible.</p> <p>To enhance sustainable production.</p>	<p>Information on the existing schemes/labels and in particular the best-in class examples</p> <p>Information on the costs and benefits from the adoption of certification schemes.</p> <p>Creation of cross-sectoral dialogue and trust.</p>
Regional bioeconomy stakeholders	<p>To improve sustainability and protect rural areas.</p> <p>To get insights on more sustainable practices and certification schemes.</p> <p>To engage more in circular economy practices.</p> <p>To make their products more sustainable.</p>	<p>Ways to integrate identified best practices into regional bioeconomy strategies</p> <p>Information on the existing schemes/labels and in particular the best-in-class examples.</p>

Scientific community	<p>To keep up with recent developments and research trends.</p> <p>To develop research practices on the fields of bioeconomy and certification processes.</p> <p>To identify research gaps for further research.</p>	<p>New research findings along with their importance for the scientific community.</p>
NGOs	<p>To stay up to date regarding the latest trends in the sector.</p> <p>To have access to results regarding the benefits from the adoption of certification schemes.</p> <p>To engage and inform more citizens about sustainable bio-based products.</p>	<p>The positive impact from the adoption of certification schemes and labels for the industry, the local community and the environment.</p> <p>Ways to integrate the best practices derived from the project into regional bioeconomy practices</p>
International organizations	<p>To stay informed about the progress regarding the adoption of sustainability certifications for bio-based systems.</p> <p>To have access to data regarding the benefits from the adoption of sustainability certification schemes.</p>	<p>Data regarding the cost and benefits of the adoption of sustainability certification schemes.</p> <p>Data on the global trade flows for biological resources and for biobased materials and products (distinguishing between certified and uncertified).</p>
Relevant EU projects & initiatives	<p>To exchange knowledge with other experts in the sector.</p> <p>To share their results and promote their concept to other initiatives and the general public</p> <p>To establish synergies and expand their network</p>	<p>Deliverables with the project results that can be as input in further research on the topic.</p> <p>A network of projects that facilitates the dialogue and the collaboration between the relevant initiatives.</p> <p>Support in the dissemination of the project's results</p>
Society	<p>Increase awareness on the products with sustainability certifications</p> <p>To inform about bio-based products</p> <p>To inspire citizens to make sustainable and circular choices</p>	<p>Increased engagement of citizens in more sustainable and biobased practices</p> <p>Interesting findings from the project's results about the benefits (social, economic and environmental) from the adoption of sustainable certification schemes</p>

“The final key messages will be updated and refined throughout the project based on the experience acquired during its implementation”

5. Communication and dissemination tools and channels

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED’s DCP will deploy multiple tools and channels in order to ensure that activities and produced outcomes will reach a wide variety of stakeholders and will contribute to the promotion of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and labels. Below an overview of the different tools, channels and planned dissemination activities is presented that showcase **HOW** the D&C strategy will be implemented.

Figure 4. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED’s communication activities

The SUSCTCERT4BIOBASED promotional material and graphical identity includes:

- Project’s logo
- Project’s visual and graphical identity
- Trifold leaflet
- Poster
- Presentation template
- Publication template
- Letterheads
- Promotional video
- Ad hoc promotional material (tailored to the project’s activities and needs – if needed)

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED online presence includes:

- Web portal
- Bi-annual Newsletter

- Facebook page
- Twitter account
- LinkedIn profile
- YouTube channel

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED events include:

- Engagement events
- Participation in external events and conferences as SUSTCERT4BIOBASED representatives
- Present SUSTCERT4BIOBASED in external events and conferences
- Final dissemination event
- Co- organization and participation in events with projects that we have established synergies
- Organization of the Network of Interest meetings
- Organization of project’s workshops and webinars

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED publications include:

- Project’s deliverables
- Scientific publications
- Other publication in different media (e.g., articles, press release etc.)

Specific tools and channels will be used for communicating and disseminating the project’s activities and outcomes to the identified target groups. Below are presented in a summarized way:

Table 4. Tools and channels used for the identified target groups

Target Group	Tools and channels
Sustainability system actors	NoI, project events, workshops, SMAs, newsletter, promotional video, leaflet, poster, web portal, project’s reports
Policy actors	NoI, project events, external events, workshops, SMAs, leaflet, poster, project’s reports, personal contacts
Industrial actors	NoI, project events, external events, workshops, SMAs, newsletter, promotional video, leaflet, poster, web portal
Regional bioeconomy stakeholders	NoI, external events, workshops, SMAs, newsletter, promotional video, leaflet, poster, web portal
Scientific community	External events, SMAs, newsletter, promotional video, leaflet, poster, web portal, scientific publications, project’s reports, synergies with other projects
NGOs	External events, SMAs, web-portal, Newsletter, project’s reports, synergies with other projects, NoI, leaflet, poster
International organizations	External events, SMAs, web-portal, project’s reports, scientific publications, external events

Relevant EU projects & initiatives	External events, SMAs, newsletter, promotional video, leaflet, poster, web portal, scientific publications, project's reports, synergies with other projects, NoI
Society	External events, SMAs, newsletter, promotional video, leaflet, poster, web portal

The following sub-chapters offer a detailed description of the abovementioned tools and channels.

5.1 Promotional material

The promotional material of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED was prepared during the early stages of the project. WHITE was responsible for the graphic design and the content, while the consortium partners offered feedback throughout the development process. **The material will be freely available to the public through the project's website** (online for download) and the partners will print it when needed. The material will be used during physical activities (including external and project's events) to attract and engage relevant stakeholders and give more information on the project's mission and objectives.

All the promotional material is designed based on the project's unique identity that is presented in the following paragraph.

5.1.1 Project logo

The project's logo and visual identity have been developed at the beginning of the project (**M1**). The produced promotional and communication material (such as leaflet, poster, templates, website, publications etc.) of the project are in line with the official project's identity. After internal discussions - and with the agreement of all partners - the final logo was selected (more information in D6.2: SUSTCERT4BIOBASED promotional package). The final logo is presented below:

Figure 5. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project logo

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED logo should be visible to all the communication material produced in the framework of the project (presentation, deliverables etc.). Similarly, the EU funding should be properly acknowledged, and the EU emblem should also be properly depicted in all communication material.

Figure 6. The EU funding properly acknowledged.

The EU flag will be always accompanied by the following statement: “Funded by the European Union”

5.1.2 Leaflet and poster

A trifold leaflet and a poster (presented in D6.2: SUSTCERT4BIOBASED promotional package) were prepared to be distributed by the partners in physical events and activities but also to be uploaded on the project’s website. Both the poster and leaflet will be used to attract stakeholders’ attention and provide brief information about the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project.

The leaflet presents the project’s aim to fill the research gap on the harmonization of certification schemes, presents its vision and its impact, as well as the stakeholders who will benefit from its implementation. The poster focuses more on attracting the stakeholders’ attention with graphical elements and offers some basic information on the project and the key stakeholder groups.

Both promotional products provide information about the partners involved, together with their contact details, website and Social Media Accounts (SMAs) as well as acknowledge the funding the project receives through the Horizon Europe program.

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website visitors could easily download the leaflet and the poster.

5.1.3 Publication templates

Besides the poster and the leaflet, templates (presented in D6.2: SUSTCERT4BIOBASED promotional package) have also been prepared in line with the graphical identity of the project to be used during dissemination activities. The developed templates include:

- The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED **presentation template** (to be used by the consortium partners during events and meetings)
- **Reports template** (to be used for the project’s deliverables and other publications)
- **Letterheads** (to be used for official invitation to events)

All partners should use the official project’s templates when preparing presentations or reports in the framework of the project.

5.1.4 Promotional video

The promotional video of the project will be produced in M15. The video will present a short introduction to the project, its objectives and actions and will give an overview of its outcomes. The video will be uploaded to the project’s YouTube channel, the project’s website and the other SMAs.

5.1.5 Other promotional material

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED aspires to produce additional promotional material to attract the attention of the targeted groups. To this aim, material such as ad– hoc press releases, articles and publications will be developed. More specifically, press releases will be published when major achievements and

milestones are reached to inform on the progress of the project. Besides presenting key outcomes, general press – releases may also be produced to promote project events and attract media's attention.

5.2 Digital tools

Gradually, more people select to get informed through digital communication channels. To better communicate its messages, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED will focus on building a strong online presence in multiple digital platforms aiming to reach as many and diverse stakeholders as possible. In particular SUSTCERT4BIOBASED will create:

- (i) a website,
- (ii) a bi-annual newsletter,
- (iii) various SMAs

5.2.1 *SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website*

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website was launched on M5 (October 2022) and will constitute the key digital dissemination platform of the project, presenting its progress to wider audiences. The site is accessible by the general public and therefore its structure and content is designed in a user-friendly way to keep the stakeholders engaged.

Key information about the concept and the approach of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is presented, along with the team members and the members of the Advisory Board. All project's outcomes such as public reports, dissemination material and newsletters will be free to download. Since the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Network of Interest (NoI) is a key asset of the project, the website includes a dedicated section. Information about what is the NoI, which are the benefits for the members, as well as a list of the current members are included. The website will also support the online registration process by making the procedure safe and easy for everyone.

Although WHITE - as the dissemination manager - will be the overall responsible for the website management and content, all partners will contribute to the content development with news and other dissemination material. The website will remain active throughout the duration of the project and will include regular updates on the progress of the project, internal and external events, relevant projects and initiatives, reports and project's results, as well as news from the sector.

More detailed information about the website's content and structure are presented in the D6.2: SUSTCERT4BIOBASED promotional package.

5.2.2 *Newsletter*

A bi-annual newsletter will be produced in the framework of the project and will be distributed to the project's community. The newsletter will engage audience who is not familiar with social media and will keep stakeholders constantly updated about the project. The newsletter among others will include updates on the progress of the project, will introduce the project's concept and will disseminate upcoming project events and activities.

WHITE will be responsible for releasing the newsletter, but all partners will be responsible for providing input and content for each issue as requested by the dissemination manager.

Mailchimp will be employed for the development and distribution of the newsletter. Although the content of each issue will be agreed upon by the partners, in general, will indicatively include the following sections:

- An introductory section briefly describing the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project

- Progress updates/what has happened? (News for the progress of the project, project meetings, important milestones etc.)
- What is currently happening/ What is happening now? (Activities that were implemented recently, or they are still ongoing)
- A section dedicated to future developments / what is next? (upcoming events, important activities etc.)
- A section dedicated to our synergies (Presentation of relevant projects, news from other initiatives etc.)
- News from the sector

The Newsletter will be sent to all the subscribers and recipients upon its release while each issue will be also uploaded on the project's website.

5.2.3 Social Media Accounts (SMA)

Besides the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website, various SMAs were established to promote the project and its vision. Nowadays, SMAs offer the ability to build digital communities and attract followers that could transfer and multiply the project's vision even after the completion of the project. Therefore, a large pool of interested stakeholders will be actively engaged on a regular basis through SUSTCERT4BIOBASED social media accounts. In particular, the Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube accounts have been established by M2 of the project. Four different social media platforms have been selected to ensure the maximum dissemination of the results in media addressing different types of stakeholders.

The target audiences addressed by each social media channel and the specific objectives are presented in the following table:

Table 5. The target audiences addressed by each social media channel

Social Network	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Target Audience	Objectives
Facebook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scheme/Label owners • Standardisation bodies • Certification bodies • NGOs • Industrial biobased value chain actors • Biomass producers • Industrial operators and traders • Farmers • Civil Society • Entrepreneurs • General public 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Build a network of followers ➤ Update them on the project's progress and project's events ➤ Publish relevant posts
Twitter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scheme/Label owners • Standardization bodies • Certification bodies • EU policy makers • Policy advisors • Governments • Local authorities • NGOs • International Organisations • Unions • Research Centres • Research groups • Individual researchers • Universities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Communicate key messages and the project's outcomes ➤ Announce project's and upcoming events ➤ Retweet relevant content from other Horizon Europe/ H2020 projects

LinkedIn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU policy makers • Policy advisors • Research Centres • Research groups • Individual researchers • Universities • International organisations • NGOs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Present the project and boost professional and expert discussions ➤ Involve NoI
YouTube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scheme/Label owners • Standardisation bodies • Certification bodies • Industrial biobased value chain actors • Biomass producers • Industrial • Operators and traders • Farmers • Civil Society • Entrepreneurs • General public • Civil society organizations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Upload promotional video ➤ Contribute to increasing the visibility of the project

WHITE will be responsible for the management of SUSTCERT4BIOASED’s SMAs, while all partners are expected to contribute by:

- Becoming a follower (like or follow the page/profile);
- Promoting the accounts in their networks;
- Suggesting relevant profiles that SUSTCERT4BIOBASED should connect with;
- Sharing interesting articles and news;
- Promoting posts and news through the SMAs of their own organisations.

Facebook

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED’s Facebook page was established in M2. The Facebook page will be used to promote the project’s results and progress and share news about interesting topics from the sector. Different types of posts will be made including text and videos. In addition, invitations will be sent to followers for the event’s organised in the framework of the project. Specifically, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED’s Facebook account will serve as a:

- News and discussion hub where information or news related to the project and topics of bioeconomy, certification and circular economy will be shared;
- Platform to deliver updates about developments and results of the project (e.g., published reports, scientific publications, key events, activities, important achievements);
- Link to other similar groups and pages associated to relevant topics.

Figure 7. Screenshot of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED'S Facebook page

To monitor the performance of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED page, Facebook Analytics will be used.

Twitter

Similarly, the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Twitter account was launched in M2. The Twitter is an important dissemination tool for SUSTCERT4BIOBASED as it will enable us to stay updated on the news from the sector and the outcomes from relevant projects. The twitter platform will permit us to establish new synergies with similar initiatives and steer attention towards our concept. The use of hashtags allows the project's messages to reach wider audiences and the short and precise posts' text can actively engage a large pool of stakeholders. In addition, the account is excellent for the effective dissemination of events.

In this context, the Twitter account will act as a:

- General dissemination platform that will include the key messages of the project, will direct users to other project-related platforms/tools (e.g., SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's website, newsletter promotional video) and will communicate information on the project's development (upcoming events, participation to external events, project results, etc.);
- Newsfeed platform collecting and updating news from other relevant projects and organizations;
- Engage and create a community of followers interested in the topic and sector.

The project partners are expected to contribute to the Twitter account on a regular basis by retweeting its content via their personal accounts and suggesting relevant content. Twitter analytics will be used to monitor the account's performance. A snapshot of the account is provided:

Figure 8. Screenshot of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED'S Twitter account

LinkedIn

The LinkedIn platform was selected to promote the project to a more professional audience. The profile of the project was set in M2 in order to present the project and offer updates on its progress.

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED partners are expected to support the project’s LinkedIn profile and invite followers. The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED will have a more institutional approach to boost professional and expert discussions on issues of common interest by involving also the Network of Interest.

The metrics and insights provided by LinkedIn will be utilised to assess the project’s performance.

Figure 9. Screenshot of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED'S LinkedIn account

YouTube channel

The last established channel which was also created by M2 is YouTube. The project’s channel will be used to increase the visibility of the project through videos. In particular, the promotional video of the project which will be produced by M15 will be promoted through the channel to raise awareness around the project. The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED YouTube channel will focus on presenting the project’s actions and especially the results. Besides the video, the channel’s aim is to build a strong online community through the connection with other channels of EU funded projects.

5.3 Events

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED will participate in several events to promote its outcomes and expand its influence on the sector.

5.3.1 Project’s events

The events organised in the framework of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED aim to raise awareness around the concept of the project, promote the project’s results and facilitate the engagement of key stakeholders which will support the project’s activities and provide feedback on the produced

outcomes. Partners' extended networks, our social media followers, as well as key assets of the project such as the NoI will be exploited to attract participants to our events.

Among other types of events there will be in total **10 workshops** that will facilitate the project's development and will play a key role in its progress. Explicitly, the following types of events are scheduled as part of the project's plan:

Table 6. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED'S internal events

Event	WP, Task, responsible partner	Short description	Date (estimation)
1 st Dissemination Event	WP6, T6.2, WR	Aims to create awareness on the project and collect feedback from key groups	Before M18
2 nd Dissemination Event	WP6, T6.2, WHITE	Aims to present project results to stakeholders and engage them for the post-project exploitation	In M36
NoI meetings	WP6, T6.2, WHITE, support: all	To engage stakeholders, boost interaction and knowledge exchange	M12-36, biannual online meetings
<i>In total 10 workshop events will be implemented within WP1 – WP5</i>			
<i>Including the following:</i>			
Workshop	WP3, T3.2, ECOS, support: WR, CU	Present the monitoring system and collect input and feedback on the methodology	M1 - M15
Workshop	WP4, T4.2, WR, support: CU, CIRCE	To receive feedback and comments on the selection method and selected value chains	M6–M11
Workshop	WP5, T5.3, ECOS, support: WR, CU	To present and discuss on the derived recommendation on how to enhance the performance of certification schemes	M20-M36
Workshops/webinars	WP5, T5.4, CIRCE, support: WR, CU	To effectively communicate and create understanding and acceptance among the industries benefits of adoption of certification	M20-M36

Regional stakeholder workshops	WP5, T5.5, CIRCE support: ECOS, CU	To assess the potential deployment opportunities of recommendations in regional bioeconomy strategies	M20-M36
--------------------------------	------------------------------------	---	---------

5.3.2 External events and conferences

Besides organising events in the framework of the project, the consortium partners will also attend external events and conferences with the aim to reach a wide audience relevant to the sector. During these events the partners will:

- Present the project (concept, approach etc.).
- Promote the project's results.
- Promote SUSTCERT4BIOBASED actions and events.
- Establish synergies and contacts with relevant projects and initiatives.
- Engage relevant stakeholders in project's activities (e.g. NoI etc.).
- Promote the project's dissemination channels (website, SMAs etc.).
- Stay up to date on the latest technological and research findings.

The partners participating in external events should always follow the visual identity of the project and use the official promotional material (leaflet, poster, ppt template etc.). In case of participation to an external event to present the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, partners should send the final presentation to WHITE **at least 5 working days prior to the event**. In addition, the partners should always inform WHITE in advance regarding their participation in an external event to be appropriately disseminated through the project's dissemination accounts. Finally, after the implementation of the event, the partners should fill in the reporting template (Annex III) and send it back to WHITE.

An indicative list of identified conferences and events is provided below:

Table 7. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED'S external events and conferences

Conference	Short description	Link
European Biomass Conference and Exhibition	Largest biomass conference and exhibition in the world	https://www.eubce.com/
European Bioplastics	Business and discussion forum and bioplastics product exhibition	https://www.european-bioplastics.org/events/eubp-conference/
EURAS Annual Standardisation Conference	Conference which promotes standardisation research	https://www.euras.org/conference/2022-conference
World Bioeconomy Forum	Circular bioeconomy stakeholders discuss the role of bioeconomy related to climate change mitigation	https://wcbef.com/events/world-bioeconomy-forum-2022/

EU Green Week	Discussions around EU environmental policy - circular economy, biodiversity and zero pollution	https://environment.ec.europa.eu/eu-green-week-2022_en
European Forum for Industrial Biotechnology and Bioeconomy	Economic and green contribution to Europe from innovation and manufacture within industrial biotechnology and the bioeconomy	https://efibforum.com/
International Bioeconomy Conference - The European Summit	European Summit with bioeconomy related discussions	https://www.bioeconomy-conference.eu/en/
Renewable Materials Conference	Renewable materials solution - biobased, CO2 and recycled products	https://renewable-materials.eu/
Sustainable Alternative and Bio-based Materials	Summit on how to integrate alternative and bio-based materials in the market	https://biobased-alternative-materials.com/
International Consortium on Applied Bioeconomy Research	Consortium on bioeconomy, agricultural biotechnology, rural development and bio-based economy research topics	https://icabr.net/

5.4 Publications

5.4.1 Scientific publications

Scientific publications are important significant channels for presenting SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's outcomes to academic, research and industrial target audiences. Thus, creating knowledge impact and enabling other researchers and stakeholders to use the project's results in their own work contributes to disseminating the project further. Therefore, it is expected that academic partners will contribute to the drafting and writing of scientific articles.

Since the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED consortium supports open access of scientific publications, all necessary steps will be taken to ensure free access to peer-reviewed articles resulting from the project. Actions in this regard will include the following alternatives as described in the Open Data Strategy of the EC and will follow the FAIR-approach. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's research outputs will be accessible to the public in a digital and online way, and free of charge. Wageningen Research has national Open Access agreements with all major publishers. Therefore:

- i. Research deliverables will be published on the project's web portal
- ii. Scientific publications will be immediately Open accessible through a trusted repository (e.g., Open Research Europe, European Open Science Cloud) ("green" or "gold" open access).

Green open access: Deposit an electronic copy of the published version or the final manuscript accepted for publication in a scientific publication relating to the project's foreground in an institutional or subject-based repository at the moment of publication. The beneficiaries will make their best efforts to ensure that this electronic copy becomes freely and electronically available to anyone through this repository within 6 months from the publication date. The exact selection of the repository, the terms under which access will be granted, and all other relevant details will be decided when the publication is available.

Gold open access: Immediately provide the article in open access mode, with the payment of publication costs being shifted away from readers. The costs (Author Processing Charges) will be paid by the partners supporting the research.

An indicative list of scientific Journals can be found below:

Table 8. Indicative list of pre-selected scientific journals for SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's papers

Journal	Impact factor
Journal of Cleaner Production	11.072
Science of the Total Environment	10.753
Sustainable Production and Consumption	8.921
Environmental Science and Policy	6.424
Biofuels, Bioproducts & Biorefining	5.239
Sustainability	3.889

5.4.2 *Non-scientific publications*

Throughout the duration of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project, all partners will be invited to produce press and media releases, articles in mass media, presentations on TV or radio, or other media. The aim of all these efforts is to increase the project's visibility and publicity and the potential to reach out to stakeholders outside of the consortium.

Lastly, all partners are responsible for identifying publishing opportunities and for carrying out all necessary actions to ensure the promotion of project's assets and results. Additionally, this strategy does not foresee a minimum number of non-scientific publications. However, track of published material will be kept through the Dissemination Reporting Template (Annex II) on a monthly basis.

6. Roles and responsibilities

The allocation of responsibilities answers the question of **who** is going to implement the DCP. In order to achieve the defined objectives, the implementation of the dissemination and communication strategy will be a collective effort from all consortium partners. WHITE as the dissemination and communication manager monitors the implemented activities and the progress towards the realisation of the DCP objectives. Partners' contribution will be a natural by-product of the project's development as most activities, results, milestones and progress will either involve stakeholder engagement and communication or turn into assets that should be adequately promoted. The partners will contribute to the offline activities by organising events, plan dissemination activities and participate in external events and conferences to raise awareness. In addition, they are expected to be involved in the online dissemination activities by providing content and promoting the digital dissemination tools of the project. More specifically consortium partners should:

Online dissemination activities:

- Provide content for the website, SMAs and the newsletter (The contribution could be a suggestion for a Facebook or Twitter post, an article regarding the project or a relevant topic of the sector, or an interview). The goals are to ensure a constant flow of content around the project's actions and keep our online presence active and useful for the relevant stakeholders.
- Promote the website, SMAs and the newsletter through their network.
- Inform the dissemination manager about relevant events or news of the sector that could be used for content creation

Offline activities:

- Organise events and raise awareness around the project
- Disseminate the promotional material of the project (leaflet, poster, etc.)
- All partners through their participation in external events and conferences and through publications for online/ offline sources (websites, newspapers, magazines, etc.) should ensure the widest exposure and dissemination of the project.

Activities reporting:

All partners must report the carried-out dissemination and communication activities to the dissemination manager. More information for the process will follow in the respective chapter.

7. Networks and synergies

The establishment of synergies and the use of networks for the dissemination of the project's results is pivotal for its successful implementation. This need was identified from the proposal stage and therefore a dedicated task (T6.3) that aims to search for alignment with opportunities with relevant projects was drafted. Dedicated information on the synergies will be presented in two reports that will be drafted in cooperation with the other projects funded under ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07 (M18, D6.5, responsible partner: WR) and (M36, D6.6, responsible partners WR).

Over the course of the project the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED partners will:

1. Cooperate with the projects which are funded under the same call (HARMONITOR, STAR4BBS)
2. Seek and establish synergies with projects that are relevant to the topic.

The cooperation may take various forms. Indicatively:

- Mutual dissemination of events in our social media accounts and website
- Mutual reference of projects on respective websites
- Organisation of joint activities (e.g., workshops, dissemination events etc.)
- Participation in the Nol
- Participation in the project's events
- Exchange of news, experiences
- Co-participate in conferences
- Co-write press releases, articles etc.

Multiple potential joint activities will be also identified throughout the whole duration of the project and will be reported in the respective deliverable.

Even from the initial stages of the project several potential networks and relevant projects have been identified.

Table 9. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED'S dissemination networks

Consortium networks for dissemination			
<i>Sustainability system actors</i>	<i>Industry associations</i>	<i>International organisations</i>	<i>Regional bioeconomy actors</i>
ISEAL, NEN, RSB, ISCC, REDCert, SGS, GEN	BIC, EUBP, EUBA, EUBIA, ERRMA, CEFIC	OECD, FAO, UNEP, UNFSS, IRP	EIP-AGRI, BIOEAST, SPRING

The initial list will be constantly updated during the duration of the project in order to identify new opportunities for collaboration.

Table 10. Projects for potential synergies

Acronym	Title	Description	Website	Period
HARMONITOR	Monitoring certification schemes	The project aims to improve the effectiveness of certification schemes and labels in different sectors of the EU Bioeconomy.	https://www.harmonitor.eu/	2022-2025
STAR4BBS	International and EU sustainability certification schemes for biobased systems	The project aims to develop a new monitoring system for assessing the effectiveness and robustness of existing Supply Chain Sustainability (SCS) and Business-to-business (B2B) labels applicable to biological feedstock and bio-based materials and products.	Under development	2022-2025
SUSTRACK	Supporting the identification of policy priorities and recommendations for designing a sustainable track towards circular bio-based systems.	The project aims to identify environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy and improve existing assessment methodologies as well as develop guidelines and policy recommendations according to scenarios analysed in the project.	Under development	2022-2025
CALIMERO	Industry Case studies analysis to Improve Environmental performance and sustainability of bio-based industrial processes	The project aims to improve current Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) methodologies of certain sectors from bio-based industries.	Under development	2022-2025

BIORECER	Biological Resources Certifications Schemes	The project aims to evaluate the impact of current and established certification schemes on consumers and bio-based industry stakeholders.	Under development	2022-2025
ALIGNED	Aligning Life Cycle Assessment methods and bio-based sectors for improved environmental performance	The project aims to deliver a modelling framework to assess and optimise the environmental and socio-economic performance of bio-based industries.	Under development	2022-2025
FOODCost	FOOD Costing and Internalisation of Externalities for System Transition	The project redefines the value of food and provides a set of improved and harmonised analytical instruments for the valuation and internalisation of externalities.	https://www.foodcost-project.eu/	2022-2026
UPLIFT-PLASTICS	Sustainable plastics for the food and drink packaging industry	The project aims to put the European plastic packaging industry at the forefront of innovations and sustainability worldwide.	https://t.co/xAfNPweml4	2021-2025
AllThings.Bio	Game changer for the bio-based economy	The project aims to engage more citizens to be involved in bioeconomy.	https://t.co/VmYJ7WCeCY	2020-2023
BIObec	Leveraging education to unlock the EU bioeconomy full potential	The project aims to connect the bio-based industry (industrial actors and regions) and the education system (universities, innovation labs, and R&D centres).	https://t.co/UXGpOhQB6	2021-2024

MPowerBIO	MPowerBIO empowers Clusters to bring SMEs across the financial valley of death	The project empowers clusters within the bio-based industry to help SMEs secure funding by building their capacity.	https://t.co/slDwzloMvo	2020-2023
BIOSWITCH	Encouraging brand owners to switch to Bio-based	The project aims to support brand owners with a dedicated tool in order to facilitate their transition to bio-based economy.	https://t.co/LINaCGa9Gq	2020-2023
Bio - plastics Europe	Bio - plastics Europe	The project aims to deliver sustainable strategies and solutions for bio-based plastics to support the EU-Plastic Strategy and to promote circularity in the economy.	https://www.bioplasticseurope.eu/project	2019-2023
WaysTUP!	Value chains for disruptive transformation of urban biowaste into biobased products in the city context	The project aims to demonstrate the establishment of new value chains for urban biowaste utilisation through a multi-stakeholder approach.	https://waystup.eu/	2019-2023

8. Monitoring, Evaluation and reporting framework

8.1 Monitoring and evaluation

The monitoring mechanisms are crucial to secure the successful implementation of the D&C strategy and ensure the achievement of the DCP goals: in essence, they measure the impact of the dissemination efforts. Therefore, a monitoring process has been set up at the beginning of the project. This process will support us to identify any potential gaps and problems, special needs of relevant stakeholders and good practices that we can adopt. The DCP will be updated - if needed - to include all the modifications and changes due to the monitoring process. In this way, we aim to ensure the effective dissemination of the outcomes to the project's key stakeholders and the general public.

A set of KPIs were selected to evaluate the impact of the DCP activities. Of course, the metric targets and the needs will be adjusted to the project's results and will be included in the updated deliverable (M36). The dissemination manager with the support of the consortium partners will keep track of the quantitative metrics during the reporting periods. In addition, qualitative feedback after the implementation of events will be also requested by the partners to better evaluate the strategy and proceed with modifications if deemed necessary.

Below is presented the list of KPIs for the dissemination and communication activities of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED:

Table 11. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED'S Key Performance Indicators

Assessed element	Metric	Target
Visits to SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website	Nr of visits (total)	> 10,000
Social media accounts (LinkedIn, YouTube, Facebook, Twitter)	Nr of followers	> 1,000
	Nr. of impressions	> 30,000
Newsletter	Nr. of published Newsletters	6
	Nr. of subscribers	> 200
Network of Interest	Nr. of participants	≥ 50
Project workshops	Nr. of workshops	≥ 10
Participation to external events	Nr. of events	≥ 10
Promotional video	Nr. of views (total)	> 500
Synergies with other initiatives	Nr. of joint actions	10

Engagement events	Nr. of events	2
	Nr. of participants	> 50

8.2 Reporting

Keeping track of the dissemination, communication and engagement activities that were carried out by all partners in the framework of the project is fundamental for its successful implementation. Therefore, the reporting and documentation is very important for the DCP. In particular, throughout the duration of the project, all consortium partners should report their dissemination and communication activities on a monthly basis by filling in the template shared by WHITE (online in the project's repository). Each semester (M6, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36) WHITE will consolidate the results and will develop the semestrial technical reporting of WP6.

For keeping track of the activities performed by the consortium partners, three documents have been designed and shared (Annex).

Table 12. List with Annexes for Dissemination

Annex	Dissemination Tool	Coverage	When
Annex II	Dissemination reporting template	All the dissemination activities carried out by the partners every month.	Every month
Annex III	Event's reporting template	Each single event organised by the partners or where the partners participated.	Within 30 days after the implementation of the event
Annex IV	External conferences and Events template	Any external event/conference that it is relevant to our project and with potential benefit to attend	Throughout the project (ad- hoc basis)

Dissemination reporting template: This template will record all the dissemination and communication activities of the project. The document should be updated by all partners on a monthly basis. Keeping track of the activities will ensure that any problems or gaps will be observed early, and mitigation measures will be put in place in order to be solved.

Event reporting template: This template should be filled by all partners whenever they organise or participate in an event (e.g., workshop, conference, meeting etc.). The template should be sent to WHITE no later than 30 days after the implementation of the event. Moreover, the events should be always communicated to WHITE in advance for promotional purposes.

The external conferences and Events template: This is a template that facilitates the identification of events (workshops, conferences, webinars) with topic relevant to the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED vision. Each partner should fill in this template and send the information to WHITE when identifies any event or conference that could be useful for the consortium (e.g., attend, present etc.).

Each project partner should immediately contact WHITE, should any risks be identified concerning communication and dissemination activities, or in case problems arise during the implementation of publicity actions.

9. Timeline and implementation plan

The dissemination and communication activities started at the beginning of the project with the production of the promotional material, will continue with a wide deployment of off-line and online dissemination activities and will be completed with the promotion of the project’s final results. On top of that, the project’s findings will be promoted even after the end of the project. Below you may find the four different periods during which all our dissemination and communication activities will be implemented:

Figure 10. Summary of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED'S timeline

❖ First phase – early in the project (M1-M6):

During the first phase of the project, the D&C strategy was designed. In the framework of the D&C strategy, several key aspects were identified such as the targeted stakeholder groups that will be reached during the project, as well as the messages that will be used to engage them. In addition, the selection of suitable metrics for monitoring the successful implementation of the strategy took place, and the consortium partners' responsibilities were clearly defined. Furthermore, besides developing the D&C strategy, the first months of the project were dedicated to the production of the dissemination material, as well as the establishment of the dissemination and communication tools. The project's visual identity and logo, the promotional material (leaflet, poster, templates, Letterheads), the SMAs and the project's website were developed the first 5 months of the project. Finally, a first dissemination of the project to the broader public will take place through contacts with other projects, press releases, the first newsletter and by participating in external events.

❖ **Second phase – during the project (M7 - M25):**

Throughout the project, constant interaction between the project partners and the relevant stakeholders will be established. An active community interested in the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project will be created and maintained through the SMAs and the project's NoI. In addition, synergies will be developed with other projects and initiatives relevant to the topics of bioeconomy, bio-based material and industry, sustainability and circular economy and certification schemes and labels. Multiple activities are planned to take place within the second phase of the project including dissemination events, workshops, webinars, Network of interest meetings, joint events, and dissemination activities with the sister projects. Publications and promotion of the project's results through the website and the bi-annual Newsletter will further maximise the project's impact. Finally, the participation of consortium partners in external events and conferences, as well as their connections to key networks from the sector will be leveraged in order to promote the project to a wider audience.

❖ **Third phase – at the end of the project (M26 - M36):**

Although the dissemination of the project's vision will continue, this phase of the project will mainly focus on the dissemination of the project's results and outcomes. In particular, towards the end of the project, the data and lessons learnt will permit consortium partners to draft some key recommendations that can support the adoption of sustainability certification schemes. The project's community (NoI, SMAs), established during the second phase of the project, will be further engaged to ensure its continuation after the project's completion. Furthermore, a final event will be organised aiming to present the project's results and engage relevant stakeholders to the post - project exploitation of the findings.

❖ **Fourth phase – Beyond the end of the project:**

The ambition of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED consortium is to continue promoting the project's vision and results even after the official end of the project ensuring that project's outcomes will reach as many relevant stakeholders as possible. Relevant publications will further disseminate the project's legacy even after the official completion.

Table 13. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's Timeline and objectives

Phase	Objectives	Dissemination tools to be used
1 st Phase (M1-M6)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Design the D&C strategy of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED 2. Design the logo and the visual identity of the project 3. Prepare the promotional package (leaflet, poster, templates, letterheads) 4. Set – up the project's digital dissemination tools (social media accounts, website) 5. Announce the project widely 6. Set up the first synergies with relevant projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project's DCP - Project's logo - Project's website - Project's SMAs - Project's poster, leaflet, presentation and report templates, letterheads - Project's press release - Project's newsletter - Contact with other projects and networks - Participation in external events

<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">2nd Phase (M7 -M25)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Widely disseminate and communicate the project's concept and progress 2. Engage a wide variety of stakeholders 3. Establish synergies with several relevant projects 4. Built an active community to exchange knowledge and updates on the project and the sector 5. Promote the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and labels 6. Present the best-in- class certification schemes and labels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project's logo - Project's website - Project's SMAs - Project's poster, leaflet, presentation and report templates, Letterheads - Project press release and publications - Project's Newsletter - Nol - Project's video - Project's internal events, workshops and webinars - Project's synergies with other relevant projects - Participation in external events and conferences
<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">3rd Phase (M26 -M36)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Effective dissemination of the project's outcomes 2. Facilitate the adoption of the project's outcomes 3. Dissemination of the project's policy recommendations 4. Engage the relevant stakeholders to ensure the exploitation of project results after the end of the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project's logo - Project's website - Project's SMAs - Project's poster, leaflet, presentation and report templates, Letterheads - Project press release and publications - Project's Newsletter - Nol - Project's video - Project's internal events, workshops and webinars - Project's final dissemination event - Project's synergies with other relevant projects - Participation in external events and conferences

4 th Phase - Beyond the end of the project	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dissemination of project results 2. Post – project exploitation of the project’s results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consortium partners’ networks and means of communications - Engaged stakeholders and contacts of the Nol
---	--	---

10. Conclusions

The D&C strategy will serve as a guide and will assist the project partners to the dissemination and communication activities carried out during the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project.

This document presents a tailored D&C strategy and a DCP to effectively convey the key messages and actions of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED to its target audience, as well as to increase its visibility. Thus, the DCP includes all the communication activities planned during the project’s lifetime, the communication channels that will be used to achieve dissemination and the key messages.

Given the dynamic nature of the project, the DCP will be subject to feedback throughout the project’s lifecycle and will be updated in line with the needs and views of the stakeholders. The final updated version will be prepared by M36 and will enhance the project’s vision to the European community at large.

11. Annex

11.1 Annex I – Dissemination and communication guidelines

This document provides some key information regarding dissemination and communication activities and introduces the tools that will be used during the project to monitor the activities performed.

Main guidelines:

- Actively contribute to the dissemination of project results and key messages.
- Please use the wording “SUSTCERT4BIOBASED” to refer to the project.
- Please don't forget to **always include the EU logo** and the disclaimer “Funded by the European Union”

In practice, it should look like this:

When displayed with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

The EU emblem, and the funding statement, must be featured on all communication material such as printed, digital products, websites and their mobile version, for the public or the partners.

- More information on how to display the EU logo in publications and products can be found [here](#)
- You can download the EU emblem in the desired resolution following this link: https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en.

1. Partners are requested to follow carefully the above instructions, as they are a contractual obligation, (Article 17 of the GA).
2. If possible, follow the style guide concerning writing style, formatting options, numbers and currency, abbreviations and acronyms, captions, electronic cross-references, naming conventions, citation style.

In general:

- make sure to use the logo colour scheme for documents in order to ensure consistency and to reinforce the visual identity of the project.
- always use the same style for references, both for in-text citations and in the bibliography/ footnotes.

- be consistent in using currency references (for example, use EUR instead of € throughout)
 - be consistent in the numbering format; comply with the British usage (e.g., 75,000,239.23), unless differently indicated.
 - if you abbreviate a word, use the correct abbreviation (for instance, 'm' for million, not 'mn');
 - make sure to introduce each abbreviation and acronym the first time you use it and create an abbreviation/acronym list at the beginning of the document.
 - review the language and the coherence of the structure of the text you drafted.
3. Whenever possible, use the templates that will be provided to you, e.g., letterhead, presentation, publication. A leaflet and a poster will be prepared for you to use throughout the project. Other communication materials (e.g., infographics) will be prepared ad-hoc if needed.
 4. **Always** inform WHITE and WR regarding every dissemination and communication activity that you plan to carry out (e.g., organisation of an event, articles on websites or magazines, participation in an external event, etc.). This will enable us to publicise it through the project's communication channels in a timely manner.
 5. You will have to report in detail all the dissemination actions you undertook (please see **SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Dissemination Reporting Template** for instructions).
 6. Always report about meetings and events you organised and/or participated in (please see **SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Event Reporting Template** for an explanation on how to report about events).
 7. Inform WHITE and WR about relevant events (e.g., conferences, workshops, seminars etc.) in which SUSTCERT4BIOBASED partners may be interested in participating to promote or present the project. You have received an Excel (.xls) file named "**SUSTCERT4BIOBASED External Conferences and Events**". All partners are kindly requested to fill in this specific Excel file, each time they identify an event relevant to project and share it with WR.
 8. In compliance with GDPR requirements, always gather stakeholders' consent, when collecting, using and storing personal data during events/conferences. Please consider that pictures which make individuals identifiable are also considered personal data. Partners are responsible to gather participants' consent for the activities they undertake.

The above-mentioned points will be updated, when necessary, in order to be in line with the project's requirements and progress. The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED report "Dissemination and Communication strategy" (First version due in M5) includes these guidelines and will also outline the overall project's dissemination strategy and plan.

Dissemination Monitoring tools

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Dissemination reporting template

This is an Excel file (online in the project's repository [Dissemination_Reporting_Template_v1.0.xlsx](#)) that has to be updated on a monthly basis by all consortium partners. All the information required must be provided – the EC collects all these data from the Dissemination Manager. Therefore, for each activity please indicate:

- Date;
- Place;
- Short description;
- Type of activity;
- Online/physical
- Title;
- If the activity is part of the project;
- Role and description of the organisation's involvement;
- Other project partners involved;
- Type of audience;
- Size of audience per type of stakeholder group;
- Countries addressed;
- Gender of audience;
- Type of material used and quantity (e.g. number of flyers distributed);
- Other partners or external organisation involved;
- Short description of action and dissemination activities;
- Other comments;
- Relevant contacts made (if consent was given).

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED event reporting template

The event report has to be sent after every event within 30 days to both WHITE and WR. It is a structured file that includes:

- event data (title, date, venue, organisers, type and number of attendants, duration);
- goals and relevance within the project;
- organisation;
- dissemination activities;
- short minutes of the events (structure);
- outcomes of the event;
- evaluation;
- appendixes (list of participants and scanned copy of the list signed by all participants– if possible, in compliance with the GDPR, agenda, photos, presentations).

External Conferences and Events

This is an Excel file, that you can fill in each time you identify an event (e.g. conferences, workshops, seminars etc.) relevant to SUSTCERT4BIOBASED and in which SUSTCERT4BIOBASED partners may be interested in participating to promote or present the project. Please share it with WHITE and WR.

Guidelines for enhancing online presence of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

This section provides you with some key initial guidelines regarding your expected contribution and use of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website and social media accounts (SMAs).

Website

1. Collect photos and videos for all SUSTCERT4BIOBASED activities and share them with WHITE and WR, so as to make them usable on the website and on the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED SMAs.
2. Actively contribute (if possible, with 1 news item per month per partner) to the news section of the website. Please send each news item to WHITE.
3. A news item can be anything, like a link to other similar projects/activities, an article about a new regulation, a notice regarding a new policy or initiative, an article about an event etc.
4. Inform WHITE and WR regarding every event you organise or take part to for the purposes of the project (e.g., conferences, workshops, seminars etc.) and provide WHITE with a link to the event, so that it can be posted online in the dedicated section of the website.
5. Inform WHITE and WR about news articles (e.g., newspaper article, blogpost, TV interview etc.) mentioning the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project and provide WHITE with a link/scan for giving it more visibility online.

Social Media Accounts

1. Register for all SUSTCERT4BIOBASED SMAs (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube) and use them: monitor announcements and posts, comment, like and retweet.
2. Do make your own posts to foster discussion and keep the page alive.
3. Promote the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED SMAs within your network of contacts.
4. Signal to WHITE relevant profiles that we could follow (on Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn).
5. If you make a short video edit it so as to enhance the project identity (add the name of the project, the logo, the EU emblem and the disclaimer “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101059785.”). WHITE will upload it on YouTube.

The above-mentioned points will be updated, when necessary, in order to be in line with the project’s requirements and progress.

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED social media accounts	
Twitter	@SUSTCERT4BIO
Facebook	Sustcert4biobased
LinkedIn	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED
YouTube	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

11.2 Annex II – Dissemination and communication monitoring template

No. of Action	Partner	Date of activity	Basic Info		Activity details		SUSTCERT4BIOBASED related				Audience of the event/activity								Material used		Other					
			Place of activity	Short description of the action	Type of activity <i>(Choose one of the activity categories listed in the drop-down menu)</i>	Was the activity online?	Title of conference, workshop, publication, website article, etc.	Is the activity part of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED?	description of your organisation's involvement (e.g. organiser, facilitator, interviewer, speaker, dissemination author)	Other SUSTCERT4BIOBASED partners involved (use N/A if not applicable)	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Industry	Civil Society	General Public	Policy Makers	Media	Investors	Customers	Other	Overall No of participants (automatic)	Gender of Audience (no of women)	Countries addressed	Type of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED material used	Quantity of project material used (no. of copies distributed per type of project material)	Other comments (IF RELEVANT)	Significant contacts made (IF RELEVANT (name, position, organisation, add also address, tel, e-mail))
1	WR	Example 25/6/2022	Netherlands	Writer of an article that was posted on a well known Dutch online newspaper (Rijk)	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication	Online	"..."	NO	Author	N/A	100	20	5	150	30	10	5	15	20	355	200	Netherlands	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED video	N/A	The online newsletter is one of the most read websites in Netherlands.	N/A
2	WHITE	Example 15/6/2022	Brussels, Belgium	Participation to a conference organized by Organisation X in the thematic area of green tables. We participated as main promoters in a dedicated session. The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED leaflet and poster were also used during the event. Moreover, important contacts were made with relevant stakeholders.	Organization of a conference	Physical	"Title of Conference"	YES	Organiser	CRCE	5	5	3	30	1	1	10	5	0	60	20	Belgium (20), France (20), Germany (10), Spain (10)	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED leaflet	70	The participation in the event was essential since the project was introduced to important stakeholders.	1. Contact No. 1 2. Contact No.2

11.3 Annex III – Events’ reporting template

Event’s Aggregate Data

Title	
Date	
Venue	
Organizers	
Audience (number and type)	
Duration	

Stakeholders reached

What type of stakeholders were engaged?

- Define the type(s) of stakeholders reached (policy, SMEs, general public etc.)
- How many people attended?
- How many women attended?

Event’s goals, objectives and relevance with SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

What were the key objectives of this event/activity? (e.g., to gather ideas, gather data, find new stakeholders, etc). Was the event relevant to SUSTCERT4BIOBASED? To what extent?

Organisation of the event

In case of organizing a project's event. For participation in external events do not complete this section.

How was the event/activity organized?

- What steps were taken to set up the activity/event?
- What was the location of the event and why was this area selected?

Dissemination activities

How was the event/activity promoted? Was project material used for promotion? Was the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project promoted during the event?

Structure of the event (short minutes)

Description of the event's sessions.

- What did the event/activity consist of?
- What tools were used? Why were these selected?

For participation in external events, please report what you did at the event.

Outcomes of the event

What information or data was gathered as part of this activity? (a brief summary of the information/data gathered is sufficient)

What ideas were generated? (brief explanations are sufficient)

Evaluation of the event

What are the main impressions and observation that you made?

- Were there any challenges with this event/activity?
- What were the key successes of this activity?
- If re-deploying this event/activity how will/would you do it differently?

ANNEX: Attachments

- The list of participants (if consent to store and share data was given)
- A scanned copy of the list of participants signed by each participant (if possible)
- The agenda of the event
- Photos (please make sure to have the consent of participants to use them)
- Presentations (if applicable)
- Copies of materials used to promote the event (e.g., links to press releases, videos, posts, leaflets etc.

11.4 Annex IV – External conferences and events identification template

No.	Event's name	Thematic Focus	Abbreviation	Date	Location	Registration fees	Deadline for submission	Website	Specific requirements for participation (e.g. abstract submission, ...)	Added by (Partner)
1										
2										

About SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is an EU funded (Horizon Europe) project aiming at defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for industrial biobased systems to support tracing the sustainability (environmental, social, economic) of biobased products along the value chains and trades within the EU and globally for responsible production and consumption. This objective is realised by the development of a monitoring system, mapping of the current situation in global trade flows of biological resources and biobased products, and feasibility assessment from the adoption of certification schemes and labels considering actual economic as well as internalized environmental and social costs and benefits. The results of the project are leveraged to provide recommendations to four key target groups: policy makers, sustainability system community, industrial biobased value chain actors, and regional bioeconomy stakeholders. These ambitions are addressed by a strong, well-balanced and multi-disciplinary consortium comprised of 5 complementary partners. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED thereby supports the development of harmonized system requirements, continuous improvement of sustainability certification schemes and labels and contributes towards establishing a circular, climate-neutral and sustainable biobased industry.

PARTNERS

Stichting Wageningen Research (WR)
www.wur.nl

Fundacion Circe Centro de Investigacion de Recursos y Consumos Energeticos (CIRCE)
www.fcirce.es

White Research SRL (WHITE)
white-research.eu

Environmental Coalition on Standards (ECOS)
www.ecostandard.org

Control Union Certifications Germany GmbH (CU)
www.controlunion-germany.com

CONTACT US

info@sustcert4biobased.eu

Sustcert4biobased

@SUSTCERT4BIO

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

VISIT

www.sustcert4biobased.eu